

Supporting Information for ”Chemostratigraphy across the Permian-Triassic Boundary: The Effect of Sampling Strategies on Carbonate-carbon Isotope Stratigraphic Markers”

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Introduction

This supporting information file contains information regarding the biostratigraphy of the P–Tr boundary beds of Iran and China (Text S1 and Table S1) that enabled the construction of Figure 1. Furthermore, the results of a survey on published isotope stratigraphic markers that use second-order carbon isotope excursions is included (Figure 2 and Table S2). In addition, this document includes the caption of the newly produced carbonate C and O isotope dataset (Dataset S1; published separately under DOI:10.5281/zenodo.1470680), BSE images (Figures S1–S4) and the some additional statistical test (Figures S5 and S6). Data visualization and statistical data treatment have been written in the R-language. The R-scripts are made available on the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/MartinSchobben/carbonate>.

Text S1. Biochronology

Although conodont zonation schemes enable the correlation of individual localities in NW Iran and central Iran [Kozur, 2007; Ghaderi et al., 2014], globally comprehensive stratigraphic schemes are still fraught with uncertainties. For instance, conodont assemblages extracted from samples retrieved from limestone sequences in Iran and China do not yield comparable successions. This discrepancy has been related to sedimentary gaps, geographic clines and endemic species [Korte et al., 2004a; Korte and Kozur, 2010; Shen and Mei, 2010].

Nonetheless, it is possible to constrain a biochronological framework that gives at least some inter-regional stratigraphic tie points, enabling an inter-basinal comparison [Table S1; Korte et al., 2004a; Korte and Kozur, 2010; Shen and Mei, 2010]. The Wuchiapingian–Changhsingian has been defined in both the Iranian and Chinese localities [Jin et al., 2006; Ghaderi et al., 2014]. Although the index species (*Clarkina wangi*) has not been detected in the Late Permian beds of Iran, the stage boundary has been defined by a transitional fauna of *C. orientalis* and *C. subcarinata*, as found at multiple sites in Iran [Ghaderi et al., 2014]. The successive Changhsingian conodont zonation has been subject of considerable debate, and the Chinese locations are marked by a less stratigraphically resolved scheme, which misses several species that are found in P–Tr strata in Iran (e.g., *C. nodosa*, *C. bachmanni*, *C. abadehensis*, *C. hauschkei*). However, it has been suggested that some of these missing species (e.g., *C. nodosa*–*C. yini* and *C. hauschkei*–*C. meishanensis*) can be accounted for by assuming that they belong to a geographic cline of a species [Shen and Mei, 2010]. In other instances, tentative identifications suggest a more widespread occurrence of species than formerly recognized [e.g., *C. abadehensis* and

C. bachmanni found in P–Tr boundary beds exposed in China; *Lai and Mei*, 2000; *Chen*, 2007]. Still others, interpret the apparent absence of certain species in limestone successions, such as the P–Tr GSSP Meishan section, as stratigraphic incompleteness of certain sites situated in the South China basin, notably the Meishan section [*Kozur*, 2004]. In contrast to the former uncertainties, the successive Late Permian clay-rich intervals of the P–Tr successions in Iran and the Meishan section harbour comparable conodont elements, such as *Hindeodus changxingensis* [*Ghaderi et al.*, 2014; *Yuan et al.*, 2014]. Hence, these boundary clay units seem temporally correlative, and suggest synchronicity for the extinction horizon that marks the lower bound of these units [*Kozur*, 2007; *Yuan et al.*, 2014]. Whereas, the up-section; *H. parvus*, *Isarcicella staeschei* and *I. isarcica* zones are inter-regionally correlative, the remainder of the here-studied sequence is less constrained. At least the *Stepanovites kummeli* [*Cao et al.*, 2009] and *Neospathus dieneri* [*Korte et al.*, 2004a] are elements associated with the Dienerian, yielding a tentative subdivision of time-equivalent units in both the Triassic of the Meishan section and the P–Tr beds located in Iran (Table S1).

Data Set S1. Unprocessed oxygen and carbon isotope data. The sample ID is composed of a running number (1–4) plus a number that refers to the sequence in the sampling-grid, where the grid is numbered 1–25 from left-to-right and from top-to-bottom.

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Figure S1. Compiled BSE images of the *Argillaceous red, nodular, bioturbated wackestone* (Zl 11). A high-resolution version of the image can be found under DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.839676.

Figure S2. Compiled BSE images of the *Grey/yellow nodular sponge wackestone* (Zl 18a) A high-resolution version of the image can be found under DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.839676.

Figure S3. Compiled BSE images of the *Laminated bindstone* (Zl 23). A high-resolution version of the image can be found under DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.839676.

Figure S4. Compiled BSE images of the *Oncoid wackestone/floatstone* (Zl 35). A high-resolution version of the image can be found under DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.839676.

Figure S5. Quantile-quantile plot, comparing the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ distribution with a theoretical normal distribution. Note, that ZI 35 exhibits a "heavily tail", which belong to the anomalous low $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of a calcite vein.

Figure S6. Quantile-quantile plot, comparing the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ distribution with a theoretical normal distribution. Note, that ZI 11 exhibits a skewed distribution

Table S1. Biostratigraphic framework of P–Tr beds in Iran and China

Unit	Iran	China^a
K	<i>Neospathodus dieneri</i>	<i>Stepanovites kummeli</i>
J	<i>Hindeodus postparvus</i>	<i>Clarkina tulongensis</i> - <i>Clarkina planata</i>
I	<i>Isarcicella isarcica</i> <i>Isarcicella staeschei</i>	<i>Isarcicella isarcica</i> <i>Isarcicella staeschei</i>
H	<i>Hindeodus lobata</i> <i>Hindeodus parvus</i>	<i>Hindeodus parvus</i>
G	<i>Merrillina ultima</i> - <i>Stepanovites mostleri</i> <i>Hindeodus praeparvus</i> - <i>Hindeodus changxingensis</i>	<i>Hindeodus changxingensis</i>
F	<i>Clarkina hauschkei</i> <i>Clarkina abadehensis</i>	<i>Clarkina meishanensis</i>
E	<i>Clarkina yini</i> <i>Clarkina nodosa</i> <i>Clarkina bachmanni</i>	<i>Clarkina yini</i>
D	<i>Clarkina changxingensis</i>	<i>Clarkina changxingensis</i>
C	<i>Clarkina subcarinata</i>	<i>Clarkina wangi</i> - <i>Clarkina subcarinata</i>
B	<i>Clarkina orientalis</i>	<i>Clarkina orientalis</i>
A	<i>Clarkina trancaucasica</i> <i>Clarkina leveni</i>	

^a Meishan P–Tr GSSP. Sources are listed in Text S1. Biochronology

Table S2. Survey of carbon isotope stratigraphic markers in chemostratigraphic studies on P–Tr boundary beds located in

Iran, which target second-order excursions. Small: 0.3–0.5 per mill, medium: 0.5–1 per mill, large: >1 per mill.

Reference	Locality	Country	Latitude	Longitude	Material retrieval	<0.25 per mill	small	medium	large
<i>Heydari et al.</i> [2000]	Abadeh	Iran	32.53	53.12	whole	0	0	0	2
<i>Richoz et al.</i> [2010]	Ali Bashi	Iran	38.94	45.52	drill	2	1	1	1
<i>Richoz et al.</i> [2010]	Zal	Iran	38.73	45.58	drill	1	1	2	0
<i>Richoz et al.</i> [2010]	Abadeh	Iran	32.53	53.12	drill	3	1	1	0
<i>Richoz et al.</i> [2010]	Shahreza	Iran	32.12	51.96	drill	1	1	0	0
<i>Horacek et al.</i> [2007]	Abadeh	Iran	32.53	53.12	drill	1	0	0	0
<i>Horacek et al.</i> [2007]	Zal	Iran	38.73	45.58	drill	0	1	1	0
<i>Liu et al.</i> [2013]	Abadeh	Iran	32.53	53.12	whole	0	0	0	1
<i>Korte et al.</i> [2004b]	Abadeh	Iran	32.53	53.12	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Korte et al.</i> [2010]	Abadeh	Iran	32.53	53.12	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Schobben et al.</i> [2017]	Baghuk mt.	Iran	31.56	52.44	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Schobben et al.</i> [2017]	Aras Valley	Iran	39.02	45.43	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Schobben et al.</i> [2017]	Asadabad	Iran	31.85	52.18	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Schobben et al.</i> [2016]	Ali Bashi	Iran	38.94	45.52	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Schobben et al.</i> [2017]	Ali Bashi	Iran	38.94	45.52	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Korte and Kozur</i> [2005]	Ali Bashi	Iran	38.94	45.52	drill	0	0	1	0
<i>Kakuwa and Matsumoto</i> [2006]	Ali Bashi	Iran	38.94	45.52	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Schobben et al.</i> [2016]	Zal	Iran	38.73	45.58	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Korte et al.</i> [2004a]	Zal	Iran	38.73	45.58	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Schobben et al.</i> [2017]	Shahreza	Iran	32.12	51.96	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Korte et al.</i> [2004c]	Shahreza	Iran	32.12	51.96	drill	0	0	0	0
<i>Heydari et al.</i> [2008]	Shahreza	Iran	32.12	51.96	whole	0	0	0	0
<i>Baud et al.</i> [1989]	Ali Bashi	Iran	38.94	45.52	whole	0	0	0	0